

**A SURVEY OF HATE SPEECH IN SELECTED TIV POLITICAL
CAMPAIGN SONGS**

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Abstract

The study, "A survey of hate speech in selected Tiv political campaign songs" affirms language as a powerful tool used to arouse political emotions by poets specialised in composing political songs. Nigerian politicians use political songs to canvass for votes. These songs are usually sponsored by candidates or political parties, and as the proverbial saying goes "He who pays the piper dictates the tune", the poets project the image of their sponsors positively and tarnish that of their opponents in order to record victory at the polls for their sponsors. Thus, a number of political songs in Tiv are characterised by hate speech and character assassination which have the potency of causing political crises in the society. The study sets out to explicate the concept of hate speech which is a product of language and the concept of pragmatics which takes care of embedded meanings in hate speech based on the context of language use. Data for the study were collected through the primary source where Tiv native speakers were interviewed and tapes of the selected songs were listened to. Hate speech was identified in selected political songs of Terkula Kyumbul, ACN song composer, Gabon Akuhe, PDP song composer; EL-Stuffy (Awambe-a-Tiv), APC song composer and Alfred Chado (Swen-u-Tiv), PDP song composer. Data analysis of excerpts from the selected songs was based on the Speech Act Theory by J. L. Austin. The researchers found out that the Tiv political campaign songs of PDP, ACN and APC used between 2011 and 2018 in Benue State were characterised by hate speech which could cause violence prior to and after the elections.

Keywords: Language, Pragmatics, Tiv and Hate Speech

Résumé

Une enquête sur le discours de haine dans certaines chansons de la campagne politique au pays Tiv

Cette étude affirme que le moyen linguistique est un outil puissant utilisé pour susciter des émotions politiques par des poètes spécialisés dans la composition de chansons politiques. Les hommes politiques nigériens utilisent des chansons politiques pour solliciter des votes. Ces chansons sont généralement parrainées par des candidats ou des partis politiques parce que comme dit l'adage "Celui qui paie a le droit de décider comment son argent sera dépensé". Les poètes chantent la louange de leurs sponsors positivement et ternissent celle de leurs adversaires afin d'avoir la victoire aux urnes pour leurs sponsors. Ainsi, un certain nombre de chansons politiques d'origine Tiv sont caractérisées par des discours de haine et de la diffamation qui provoquent la plupart du temps des crises politiques dans la société. L'article vise à expliquer le concept du discours de haine qui est issu du langage et du concept de la pragmatique, prenant en compte les significations intégrées de ce dernier en fonction du contexte de l'utilisation du langage. Les données de l'étude ont été collectées à travers les locuteurs d'origine Tiv qu'on a interrogé et des chansons sélectionnées ont été écoutées. Le discours de haine a été identifié dans certaines chansons politiques de Terkula Kyumbul, compositeur de chansons du parti politique ACN, Gabon Akuhe, compositeur de chansons du parti politique PDP; EL-Stuffy Awambe, compositeur de chansons d'origine Tiv du parti politique APC et Alfred Chado (Swen-u-Tiv), compositeur de chansons pour le PDP. L'analyse des données d'extraits des chansons sélectionnées était basée sur la théorie de l'acte de parole de J.L. Austin, en tenant compte de l'aspect de l'acte locutoire, de l'acte illocutoire et de l'acte perlocutoire de la théorie. Les chercheurs ont découvert que les chansons de campagne politique d'origine Tiv des partis politiques PDP, ACN et APC utilisées entre 2011 et 2018 dans l'État de Benue étaient caractérisées par des discours de haine qui pourraient provoquer des violences avant les élections; et que les chansons de campagne politique ont le pouvoir de provoquer des crises politiques dans l'État même après les élections.

Mots clés : Langage, pragmatique, Tiv, discours de haine

Introduction

Elections in Nigeria are usually marred by violence which major cause is hate speech. Similarly, it has been observed that elections in Africa in general are frequently marred by violent activities. This is as a result of the adoption of a multiparty system of democracy where even within a political party, several candidates vie for the same position. It is not an overemphasis to say that Nigerian politicians reward poets whose political songs are characterised by hate

speech provided their own image is projected and that of their opponents is tarnished. Hence, hate speech which is a product of language is common in political songs produced in Nigeria, particularly in Tiv political songs. Hate speech results in fights mostly among youths who are supporters of different political parties and sometimes even members of the same political party engage in fights where there are party factions.

Language is the medium through which human beings communicate with one another. Onuoha (2020) seems to suggest that human experience and art are communicated through language. It is, therefore, an important tool to humanity. Put differently, language is the tool which facilitates the understanding and expression of feelings, opinions, and plans among others. In fact, it is through language that unity and peace are established in the society on the one hand while through it unity and peace are threatened on the other hand. Therefore, language creates an atmosphere of hatred, acrimony and suspicion in the society when not properly used. Every utterance of man carries a meaning whether in a direct or indirect manner. In most of the political songs, the composers apply the use of figurative language to tarnish the image of whoever is the target. This could be found in Gabon Akuhe's song where a Tiv man whose name is not mentioned is referred to as Miyetti Allah (The Association of Cattle Breeders dominated by the Fulanis) as if he is the founder of the association whereas this man in question is not even known for rearing cattle. Hence, this study is designed to examine hate speech in selected songs composed for People's Democratic Party (PDP) and All Progressive Congress (APC) (which is a merger of ANPP, ACN and CPC).

Conceptual Review

Despite the fact that we use language every day, we cannot define the concept 'language' in the same way. Thus, so many scholars have defined language in different ways. Amidom as cited in Denham and Lobeck (2013:2) says that 'language is a means of getting an idea from your brain into another person's brain without surgery'. This implies that language is the medium of transferring ideas from one human brain into the other. Agbedo (2015) submits that language is a natural ability possessed by every human being for the sole purpose of communication. He further submits that language is the unique medium through which the belief system, world-view, moral values, and virtually all the basic ingredients of any given society are passed on from generation to generation. With respect to Agbedo's views, language is the process through which human beings communicate with one another for various purposes. By extension, it denotes the relationship between linguistic expression and users in any society, hence the issue of pragmatics.

Pragmatics could be regarded as an extension of semantics since it is concerned with the study of meaning. According to Yule (2010:127 – 128), ‘pragmatics is the study of the speaker’s intended meaning’. This implies that there are aspects of meaning which depend more on contexts and communicative intentions of the speaker than the mere conceptual meaning. Furthermore, communication does not only hinge on recognising the meaning of words in an utterance, but recognising what speakers mean by their utterances.

The concept ‘Tiv’ refers to both the people and their language. Tiv is one of the minority ethnic groups that occupy part of the rolling Savannah region, popularly referred to as the Middle Belt of Nigeria (Yina, 2004). According to National Population Commission (2006) as cited in Aderogba (2012), Benue has a total population of four million, two hundred and nineteen thousand, two hundred and forty- four (4,219,244). Out of the total population of Benue indigenes, the National Bureau of Statistics (2012), submits that the Tiv people of Benue State have a total population of two million, nine hundred and forty-five thousand, nine hundred and forty-six (2,945,946). The Tiv people occupy fourteen local government areas out of the twenty-three Local Government Areas in Benue State. The Local Government Areas occupied by the Tiv people are Buruku, Gboko, Guma, Gwer, Gwer-West, Kastina-Ala, Konshisha, Kwande, Logo, Makurdi, Tarka, Vandeikya, Ukum, and Ushongo. Damkor (2018:5), supports the above assertion that ‘the ethnic group called Tiv today occupies more than half of the area and population of Benue State’.

Udu (2009) states that Tiv is a splinter group of the Bantu. It belongs to the Niger-Congo language family and is further classified as Benue-Congo language. Udu further states that the Tiv people occupy over thirty-three (33) Local Government Areas across Benue, Nasarawa, Cross-River, Plateau, and Taraba States. Taking the geographical spread and large number of speakers into consideration, Tiv Language is used for various communicative purposes just as any other we have got in the society.

Hate Speech

Several attempts have been made to explicate the concept of hate speech. However, a few of the definitions are considered in this paper. According to Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe as cited in Anthony and Anyanwu(2019), hate speech covers all forms of expressions which spread, incite, promote or justify racial discrimination, hatred, and xenophobia based on intolerance. Kukah (2015) asserts that hate speech is any communication that denigrates a particular person or group on the basis of race, colour, ethnicity, gender, disability, sexual orientation, nationality, religion or other characteristics.

Kukah further states that hate speech could be in form of any speech, gesture or conduct, writing or display and usually marks incitement, violence or prejudice against an individual or a group.

According to United Nations Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination as cited in Adibe (2015), hate speech is any speech that employs discriminatory epithets to insult and stigmatise others on the basis of their race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation or other forms of group membership. Umar as cited in Anthony and Anyanwu (2019) submits that hate speech is the act of insulting or abusing people for their religious or ethnic affiliation; expressing contempt against people because of their place of origin, desecrating their cultural or religious symbols and fabricating falsehood in order to demean other people. Suffice it to say, based on the aforementioned definitions, hate speech is any utterance that initiates or promotes hatred, acrimony and violence in the society.

It is imperative to note that hate speech is one of the major causes of political violence in Nigeria. Hence, Ezeibe (2015:6) asserts that ‘the role of hate speech has been established in Nigerian in politics’. This implies that you cannot exonerate hate speech from the series of political violence Nigeria has witnessed. It could be that the 2011 post-election violence was a manifestation of what some Nigerians said in their speeches before the elections were conducted. For example, Jason as cited in Ezeibe (2015:17) reports that ‘Alhaji Lawan Kaita, the former governor of old Kaduna State said that the North would make the country ungovernable if President Goodluck Jonathan emerged as the winner of the 2011 presidential election in Nigeria’.

Methodology

Data for the study were collected through primary sources by interviewing informants and listening to tapes of the selected political campaign songs. The study was limited to the Tiv political campaign songs of Gabon Akuhe, EL-Stuffy, Awambe-a- Tiv and Terkula Kyumbul. Excerpts in form of phrases were picked from the songs of the aforementioned Tiv political songs composers between 2011 and 2018 during electioneering campaigns in Benue State. There are many registered political parties but the All Progressive Congress (APC) (which is a merger of ANPP, ACN and CPC) and the People’s Democratic Party (PDP) are the two main rival political parties in Benue State. For this reason, only the songs of Gabon Akuhe (PDP songs composer) and EL-Stuffy (APC songs composer) and Terkula Kyumbul (ACN) were selected for the study to establish the hate speech that is prominent in Tiv political campaign songs. Data analysis was done from a descriptive perspective.

Theoretical Framework

This paper hinges on the Speech Act Theory propounded by J. L. Austin in 1962. According to this theory, meaning is discussed at the contextual level. Austin as cited in Agbedo (2015), asserts that speech acts are the actions performed through utterances. Austin says that for one to say something requires one performing three simultaneous acts; one locutionary act, one illocutionary act and one perlocutionary act. Locutionary act refers to the actual words uttered by the speaker. Illocutionary act is the intended effect of the uttered words. In other words, it is the speaker's intention of making the utterance. The intention of the speaker could be to persuade, insult, praise, flatter, inform, and convert other people. According to Alagh (2018), the illocutionary act could be described as a performative act. The perlocutionary act is the actual effect of what is said on the hearer or, better still, how the hearer reacts to what is said. Tiv political songs are composed with mere utterances, but the composers of the songs have a target to achieve and the songs attract reactions from the hearers, hence the chosen theory is suitable for the paper.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Selected Phrases from Tiv Political Songs

Terkula Ikyumbul alias TK Baba for Akume; ACN Senate Candidate in 2011

- (a) *Saan mo iyol tor Dajo tema double senator*- I am excited that Chief Dajo has won the senate election again.
- (b) ... *tor ngu a tôô akwati u shagen*- A traditional ruler will hijack a ballot box
- (c) *nan ver ken yough* – keep it in his room
- (d) *nan voto sha shima i nan*- and vote as much as he wants
- (e) *or mo nan bughun zwa*- no one has condemned the act
- (f) *ator a tyô cii de ajir a orôn sha mimi*- All the traditional rulers have stopped being fair in delivering judgment.
- (g) *Ujôôji de ajir a tôvôn sha mimi*- Judges have stopped being fair in passing judgment.
- (h) *Sha ciu mba- Power a de nam tom* – because PDP associates will sack him or her.
- (i) *Ior mba kuran tar u Nigeria de tom u eren sha mimi*- Security personnel have stopped doing their work with sincerity
- (j) *sha ciu PDP hembra cii*- because PDP has grown out of control.
- (k) ... *ka we a tsôngo ibumé-or nan ker u kwásè*- when you circumcise a foolish man, he ends up sleeping with your wife.
- (l) ... *Dajo jimin, nima cia ga*- The umbrella does not fear the great Dajo.
- (m) *Nima tôô nyaregh yasev ki kuma u* - the umbrella has taken our money to the tune of

- (n) *million deri mon i una ngohol Dajo hémén* – one million in order to lobby and snatch leadership from Dajo.
- (o) *EFCC yem hana ?*- where has EFCC gone?
- (p) *EFCC wa zwa hana ve u ungwa ga*- In what manner is EFCC handling the situation that you have heard about it?
- (q) ... *Akume kimbir senator ve...* - Akume has won the senate seat again
- (r) *Tor u party la a bugh wegh*- The chief of politics should open his palm
- (s) *Me nenge u na mende ce ken wegh yô*- let me see whether his palm has grown hair.

Discussion

By saying that ‘... *tor ngu a tôô akwati u shagenev nan ver ken yough; nan voto sha shima i nan*’, the poet is accusing some Tiv traditional rulers of electoral malpractice in Benue State, and thereby achieving his aim which is to tarnish the image of the traditional rulers, thereby, justifying the illocutionary act aspect of the Speech Act Theory. The phrase: ‘*Ujôôji de ajir a tôvôn sha mimi, sha ciu mba- Power a de nam tom*’ blames the People’s Democratic Party (PDP) for the injustice exhibited in the Nigerian judicial system due to the fear in the judicial staff of being sacked by PDP, the ruling party at that time. The poet also blames PDP for the laxity in protecting the nation through the phrase ‘*Ior mba kuran tar u Nigeria de tom u eren sha mimi sha ciu PDP hembra cii*’. The songs composer is inciting EFCC to prosecute PDP members for embezzling Nigerian money by saying ‘*EFCC yem hana? EFCC wa zwa hana ve u ungwa ga.*’ The poet calls a particular traditional ruler in Tiv nation chief of politics in the phrase ‘*Tor u party la a bugh wegh, me nenge u na mende ce ken wegh yô*’ This description may be considered as an insult to the traditional ruler in question.

Gabon Akuhe: Composed for People’s Democratic Party (PDP-2016)

- (a) *Apipi ve tumbur hembra mjirim*- APC members are more foolish than sandflies.
- (b) *Goment eren project aa jir ave ga*- Government does not execute projects in the midst of court cases filed by opponents.
- (c) *We a lagh a zua ankwagh u yan yô ya* -If you find any little food in the course of governance, eat.
- (d) *Ya shi nam m wa ken zwa-wam...* And give me too to eat.
- (e)...*mgbejime ka u wou tswen ga, mgbejime ka u tyô yam cica* ...the setback is not only your own but that of all my kinsmen.

Analysis

The saying, ‘*Apipi ve tumbur hembra mjirim*’ confirms Umar’s assertion as cited in Anthony and Anyanwu (2019) that hate speech is expressed when people are

insulted or abused. This saying is an insult on the entire APC members in Benue State and beyond, thereby, dissuading Benue people and other Nigerians from supporting the party. The saying ‘*We a lagh a zua ankwagh u yan yô,ya shi nam m wa ken zwa-wam*’ confirms Kukah’s submission that hate speech could be a form of inciting someone against another person. Through the above statement, the poet was inciting the government of Benue State against the electorates that brought the government on board. The poet is advising the governor for bad governance by saying a government does not execute projects while it has been sued by the opposition party. The governor should enjoy the dividends of his office and remember to give him (the singer) food to eat but he should forget about the development of Benue State.

- (a) *Goment ngu zugwen mbagenev ka nyi?* –Why is the government pitying some people?
- (b) *Alu or a numbe i deal a nam-* The government should strike anybody that messes up.
- (c) *Goment ngu zugwen Baja ka nyi jo?* Why is the government pitying ‘Baja’?
- (d) *Goment ngu pitying ior ka nyi jo?*–...Why is the government pitying people?
- (e) *Alu or a numbe i deal la nam-* The government should strike anybody that messes up.

Analysis

The composer is calling on the government to stop tolerating the activities of the opposition party, therefore, suggesting brutality against any member of the opposition who might oppose the incumbent government. This confirms that political campaign songs are capable of initiating violence.

Gabon 2017: Composed for People’s Democratic Party (PDP).

- (a) *nyaregh ki kimbin salary ki lun ga-* There is no money to pay salary.
- (b) *kpa ki nongon ee saa i wuhe Tor Tingir ki lun ndughlaa-* But there is more than enough money to facilitate the imprisonment of Chief Tingir.
- (c) *...tar u Benue gande u pedan sha kpuur-kom-*Benue state is too important to be placed on a log of wood.
- (d) *se dondo sha goment u second-hand, kpa se zua liba ga-*We supported the second-hand government but we did not get any benefit.
- (e) *...er goment ne a ye je, mba a er project ve igbendee ga-* This government has not executed any project since it came into power.

Analysis

In the saying ‘*tar u Benue gande u pedan sha kpuur-kom*’, the composer is calling the APC led Government in Benue State a non-performer. The composer

accuses the Benue State Government of corruption by saying ‘nyaregh ki kimbin salary ki lun ga’ ‘kpa ki nongon ee saa i wuhe Tor Tingir ki lun ndughlaa’ which confirms that hate speech is aimed at assassinating the character of the target person. Thus, the poet accuses the incumbent Benue State government of not paying salaries, but rather using the money that could have been channeled into the payment of salaries to orchestrate the imprisonment of Gabriel Suswam Tingir, the immediate past governor of the state at that time. These phrases of the song have the potency of making the civil servants work against the incumbent government, thereby resulting in truancy in the workforce and subsequent setback of Benue state as a whole.

Gabon 2018: Composed for People’s Democratic Party(PDP).

- (a) *iyange Waku ya senetô* –Waku was elected as a senator.
- (b) *gba pe shi un a kimbir-* And he was to be elected for the second term.
- (c) *kpa messenger u Miyetti Allah nungwa Waku yuhe* - However, the Miyetti Allah messenger aborted Waku’s second bid.
- (d) *Waku va gba shor,* - Waku failed in his contest for senate.
- (e) *tôô na Dr Adagba* – He supported Dr Adagba to emerge as the senator.
- (f) *...nyaregh yange ki a va hen Benue* - whenever Benue State Government got money.
- (g) *u Ortom man a wanger kwagh u salary-* for Governor Ortom to pay civil servants salaries.
- (h) *kpa or-atsonkaa a ese kera...*but the Hausa man would stop him by collecting the whole money.

Analysis

The phrase ‘*kpa messenger u Miyetti Allah nungwa Waku yuhe*’ tarnishes the image of a Tiv man who is accused of disappointing the Tiv nation by allowing himself to be used by the Miyetti Allah Cattle Breeders’ Association (whose members are predominantly Fulanis) to destroy other Tiv sons in Nigerian politics, particularly, Sen. Waku whose intention to represent his people for the second term at the House of Senate was aborted by the enemies of Tiv nation using the Tiv son(the Miyetti Allah’s messenger) in question as the instrument.

EL-Stuff: Composed for Dickson Tarkigh (PDP House of Representative Candidate for 2015 Elections.)

- (a) *Idyu ka nya teen ga-* National assembly is not the same as the business of selling land.
- (b) *Ihyarev mba vaan nya ve ooo-* Ihyarev are crying for their land oooo.
- (c) *Commissioner u teen nya,-*Commissioner who sells land.

- (d) *shagen ka nya i teen ze ooo*-Election is not the same as the business of selling land.
- (e) *hide se aa nya se oooo, u ngu or u dedoo ga*- Bring back our land ooo, you are not a good person.
- (f) *voto wase ka u Tarkighir...*- Our vote is for Tarkighir...

Analysis

Through the saying '*Idyu ka nya teen ga, Commissioner u teen nya*' the poet confirms Kukah's (2015) submission that hate speech denigrates a particular person. The poet is undermining the capability of the candidate whom he calls Commissioner for the sale of land, to represent his people at the national assembly, thereby creating the impression that Hon Tarkghir is the right candidate to be voted for the office. The phrases '*Iharev mba vaan nya ve ooo*' and '*Hide se a nya se oooo, u ngu or u dedoo ga*' are meant to incite the Iharev people against the candidate which could result in voting against the commissioner in the 2015 national assembly elections.

EL-Stuff: Composed for All Progressive Congress (APC) 2019.

- (a)... *U er nyi sha kwagh u belout? What* have you done with the bailout funds?
- (b) *M il kyom deri anieni, ior kpem oooo*- I buried eight hundred people; my people died oooo.
- (c) *U er gbenda u Gbajimba je kpa?* Have you constructed Gbajimba road?
- (d) *M il ikyom deri anieni, ior kpem oooo*.- I buried eight hundred people; my people died oooo.
- (e) *Sha Borno kpa mba kimbin salary*.-Even in Borno, salaries are paid,
- f) *Kanshio kimbi ior salary ican i bee*.-Mr Non-performer, pay salaries to eradicate poverty.
- (g) *U pine kapita u Benue u kera fa ga*.-You cannot locate the capital of Benue through inquiries.
- (h) *Anema dugh kera ka Makurdi ga*- Bats moved the capital away from Makurdi.
- (i) *Buhari ka u na kende tatii ve too*-They hijack any money Buhari allocates to Benue.
- (j) *Higir gbimiin tyo i vaan ye*- There is confusion everywhere so the kinsmen are crying.
- (k) *Benue, nyaregh yasev yem China ve oooo*.- Benue, our money has been taken to China oooo.
- (l) *Ior mba la ka Ior-China ooo*.-Those people are Chinese oooo.

Analysis

The poet is inciting the Gbajimba community against the governor, who hails from the same community by saying '*U er gbenda u Gbajimba je kpa ?*' 'In asking the addressee what he did with the bailout funds he had received and whether he has constructed Gbajimba road (road to the governor's community), the composer could be accusing the addressee (the incumbent governor of Benue State) of embezzling government funds. And for the composer to credit the response '*M il ikyom deri anieni, ior kpem oooo*' to the addressee is an exaggeration aimed at tarnishing the governor's image because the buried corpses were not up to eight hundred. The poet is inciting Benue people against the governor and accusing him of corruption. He is also inciting Benue State civil servants against their governor by alerting them that if Borno State which is the worst hit of Boko Haram insurgency could pay salaries, their governor should not make excuses for non-payment of salary, claiming he has buried 800 people. Having said that '*U pine kapita u Benue u kera fa ga; anema dugh kera ka Makurdi ga; Benue, nyaregh yasev yem China ve oooo*' implies that the governance of Benue state is being carried out from China instead of Makurdi and Benue money being siphoned to China by the governor. According to informants interviewed at Daudu, this song caused series of fights at Daudu, Ude and Yelewata prior to the 2019 general elections because whenever the phrase *m il ikyom deri anieni, ior kpem oooo* was sung, it reminded the bereaved, whose relatives and friends were massacred by the Fulani herdsmen and buried through the mass burial arrangement by the Benue State Government, of their late loved ones. Whenever this song was sung, the bereaved angry youths would launch an attack against the APC supporters, who would react to the attack, thereby resulting in bloodshed, but no case of death was recorded during any of the fights.

Alfred Chado (Swen-u-Tiv) Composed for Orker-Jev and Ortom: PDP Candidates, 2018.

- (a) ...*Ashabugu kwagh wou bee ve*- Ashabugu, your issue has ended.
- (b) *kwagh u senetô wou vande kulen pepe*. -Your issue as a senator finished since morning.
- (c) *Benue lumun Ortom, ve lumun Jev* - Benue has endorsed the candidature of Ortom and that of Jev,
- (d) *Se mba yan ka u bunden ga*. -we are going to get victory at the polls; nothing can prevent it.
- (e) *Senatô u zone B kaa u cie se*. - The senator for zone B cannot intimidate us.
- (f) *a er gomna ayom anieni*-He was the governor for eight years.

- (g) *shi a er senato ayom pue kar nyor kyundu.* - And he has been a senator for more than ten years, close to twenty years...
- (h) *de m lam a senetô Ashaki a nam ato.*-Let me talk to Senator Ashaki.
- (i) *u hemen Benu eanyom nga ngeen....*-You have ruled Benue for a good number of years now.
- (j) *Ankompeni ... kpa ngu ga.*-Even a small company we do not have.
- (k) *Imbya-or la se venda*-We reject that kind of person.
- (l) *u er gomna ayom imongo imongo*- You ruled as a governor for so many years.
- (m) *shi u er senetô ayom pue-kar*- And represented Benue at the National Assembly for more than ten years.
- (n) *Ganden-wam, ka nyi u ne se?*- My elder, what have you done for us?
- (o) *U shir sha u teen tyô ngohol nyaregh*-Your target has been to sell your fellow Benue people and collect money.
- (p) *Shi timin se Tiv*-And to kill Tiv people.
- (q) *U er senetô la kuma.*-Your tenure as a senator has elapsed.
- (r) *Hide ken ya, u wua se ior*,-Come back home, you killed our people.
- (s) *U tim se ufada mba vaan .-* You killed our Catholic priests.
- (t) *Kpa Ter Aondo u Sha u na kule ijir yough*- But God Almighty will pass a judgement on your case.

Discussion

The composer confirms the report by Adibe (2015) that hate speech employs discriminatory epithets to insult and stigmatise others on the basis of their race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation or other forms of group membership by calling a serving senator ‘Ashabugu(drunkard)’ and saying ‘*Utim se ufada mba vaan*’. He addresses the incumbent senator with two pejorative names; Ashabugu and Ashaki as well, making the electorates feel that the senator has not represented Zone B well at the National Assembly, so they should not vote for him in the 2019 elections but rather vote for another candidate (Orker-Jev).The poet also accuses the incumbent senator of betraying Benue people for his selfish interest and being responsible for the serial killings that took place in Benue State, particularly the killing of the two Catholic priests during Mass at St Ignatius Catholic Church, Mbalom in Gwer West Local Government Area of Benue State by suspected Fulani herdsmen.

Conclusion

The paper has surveyed hate speech in Tiv political campaign songs of Gabon Akuhe, Swen-u-Tiv , Terkula Kyumbul and El-Staffy of People’s Democratic Party (PDP) and All Progressive Congress (APC) respectively. The study discovered that both PDP and APC used hate speech in their campaign songs.

Having examined the content of the selected songs, the researchers observed that both political parties aimed at tarnishing the image of its opponent through the songs, and the nature of the hate speech had the potency of causing political crisis and even leading to the death of many people.

Recommendations

The paper recommends that Tiv poets who compose political campaign songs should moderate their use of language, avoid character assassination by hate speech in order to avert political crises in Benue State. The paper also recommends that political Tiv song poets should avoid the use of linguistic elements that can trigger political emotions and hatred among the populace. Benue State government should legislate on hate speech and punish the promoters and sponsors of the ugly practice to check the spread of hate speech which has become part of Benue State politics. Traditional rulers should also caution political songs composers in their domain against excessive use of abusive language.

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